

Figure 1

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SP P62812 GBRA1_MOUSE	RSVVVA-EDGSRLNQYDLLGQTVDSGIVQS-	<u>STGEYVVMTHFHLKRKIGYFVIQTYLPC</u>	260
SP P26048 GBRA2_MOUSE	DSVQVA-PDGSRLNQYDLLGQSIGKETIKS-	<u>STGEYVMTAHFHLKRKIGYFVIQTYLPC</u>	261
SP P26049 GBRA3_MOUSE	KSVEVA-QDGSRLNQYDLLGHVVGTEIIRS-	<u>STGEYVVMTHFHLKRKIGYFVIQTYLPC</u>	286
SP Q9D6F4 GBRA4_MOUSE	KSVEVP-KESSSLVQYDLIGQTVSSETIKS-	<u>ITGEYIVMTVYFHLRRKMGYFMIQTYIPC</u>	267
SP Q8BHJ7 GBRA5_MOUSE	KSVVVA-EDGSRLNQYHLMGQTVGTENIST-	<u>STGEYTIMTAHFHLKRKIGYFVIQTYLPC</u>	268
SP P16305 GBRA6_MOUSE	YSVEVP-EESSLLQYDLIGQTVSSETIKS-	<u>NTGEYVIMTVYFHLQRKMGYFMIQIYTPC</u>	251
SP P50571 GBRB1_MOUSE	A---VTGVNKIQLPQFSIVDYKMSKQVEF-	<u>TTGAYPRLSLSFRLKRNIGYFILQTYMPS</u>	254
SP P63137 GBRB2_MOUSE	A---VTGVTKIQLPQFSIVDYKLITKKVVF-	<u>STGSYPRLSLSFRLKRNIGYFILQTYMPS</u>	253
SP P63080 GBRB3_MOUSE	A---VTGVERIELPQFSIVEHRLVSRNVVF-	<u>ATGAYPRLSLSFRLKRNIGYFILQTYMPS</u>	254
SP Q9R0Y8 GBRG1_MOUSE	--VEVADPKYWRLYQFAFVGLRNSTEISHT-	<u>ISGDYIIMTIFFDLSRRMCGYFTIQTYIPC</u>	281
SP P22723 GBRG2_MOUSE	--VEVDTRSWRLYQFSFVGLRNTEVVKT-	<u>TSGDYVMSVYFDLSRRMCGYFTIQTYIPC</u>	282
SP P27681 GBRG3_MOUSE	--VEAADQKSWRLYQFDFMGLRNTEIVTT-	<u>SAGDYVVMTIYFELSRRMCGYFTIQTYIPC</u>	264
SP P22933 GBRD_MOUSE	Q---IHGLDRLQLAQFTITSYRFTTELMNFKS	<u>SAGQFPRLSLHFQLRRNRGVYIIQSYMPS</u>	258

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